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Changes in the Coastal Wind Field and River Runoff Conditions Expose Kongsfjorden (Svalbard) to the Influence of Atlantic Water

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Key Points:

- The heat content (HC) in Kongsfjorden waters has increased over in 1999–2020 mainly due to an increasing contribution of Atlantic Waters
- Positive temperature and salinity trends in Kongsfjorden match those observed in nearby Isfjorden but not those of the Atlantic current
- Changes in the coastal wind field and glacier meltwater runoff contribute to increase HC by altering circulation patterns

Supporting Information:

Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

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Abstract Kongsfjorden is located in West Spitsbergen, Svalbard archipelago. Its hydrography is influenced by the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) transporting warm and saline Atlantic Water (AW) toward the Arctic basin. We assessed changes in fjord water properties over two decades (1999–2020) using summer hydrographic surveys performed by the Norwegian Polar Institute in the fjord, the adjacent shelf, and open ocean regions. The heat content (HC) and salinity within the fjord have increased driven by a larger inflow of AW. These trends are consistent with observations in neighboring Isfjorden but not mirrored in the properties of the WSC over the same timeframe. Therefore, hydrographic changes in these two fjords can be attributed to larger AW intrusions rather than variations in the upstream WSC properties. We hypothesize that the increased HC in Kongsfjorden is driven by shifts in the synoptic wind patterns and larger glacier meltwater release enhancing fjord shelf exchanges. Idealized modeling experiments revealed that although these modifications contribute by increasing the fjord's HC, they explain only a small portion of the observed changes, suggesting that the availability of Atlantic Water on the shelf is the dominant factor.

Plain Language Summary The water properties of Kongsfjorden (Svalbard), whose hydrography is influenced by the warm and salty Atlantic current, have been examined over two decades (1999–2020) using summer surveys. The research reveals that the fjord's heat contents (HCs) and salinity are increasing due to a larger and purer inflow of Atlantic Water. Similar changes were observed in neighboring Isfjorden but not in the Atlantic current. We suggested that intensified Atlantic Water intrusions, and not upstream variations in the Atlantic current, drive changes in these fjords. The study examines two potential factors driving such changes: modifications in the coastal wind patterns and enhanced glacier meltwater release. Modeling experiments showed that these factors enhance the transport of Atlantic Water into the fjord. However, the main factor driving the fjord's HC appears to be the availability of Atlantic waters close to the fjord.

1. Introduction

The Arctic is the region of the Earth warming at the fastest pace (Andersen et al., 2020; Serreze & Barry, 2011). Moreover, the European Arctic is experiencing an *Atlantification* process, that is, the northward expansion of the Atlantic domain with consequent changes in the structure of the water column and ecosystems (Árthun et al., 2012; Lind et al., 2018; Polyakov et al., 2017). The Svalbard archipelago is located on the eastern edge of the Fram Strait, the main gateway between the Atlantic and the Arctic Ocean. Spitsbergen is the main island of the archipelago characterized by deep and large fjords (Kongsfjorden, Isfjorden, Bellsund, and Hornsund) opened toward the Fram Strait. The hydrography of these fjords is largely influenced by cold and fresh Arctic Water (ArW), carried by the Spitsbergen Polar Current (SPC) (Helland-Hansen & Nansen, 1909) on the West Spitsbergen Shelf (WSS), and warm and salty Atlantic Water (AW), and transported by the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) along the continental slope (Figure 1a).

The WSC has weak vertical shear and steady directions along the isobaths (Walczowski & Piechura, 2007). This current shows a strong seasonality with the highest temperatures in early autumn, between September and October. An increase in the WSC temperature of 0.8°C has been observed over the 1997–2010 period even though its properties and structure undergo large interannual variability (Beszczynska-Möller et al., 2012). The SPC flows northward close to the coast on the shallowest part of the WSS, parallel to the WSC, carrying ArW and sea

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ice from the Barents Sea through Storfjorden. The polar front, between AW and ArW on the WSS, is identified by sharp zonal temperature and salinity gradients. The interplay between the WSC and the SPC determines the amount of heat and salt transported toward West Spitsbergen fjords (Saloranta & Haugan, 2004; Svendsen et al., 2002).

Kongsfjorden (Figure 1b) is situated on the north-western side of Spitsbergen without a sill at its mouth and with several tidewater glaciers (Tverberg et al., 2019). A prominent trough on the shelf, Kongsfjordrenna, facilitates water exchanges between the fjord and WSC typically forced either by internal or external mechanisms (Tverberg et al., 2019). Density variations on the WSS develop horizontal pressure gradients between the fjord and the shelf driving baroclinic currents, which adjust the stratification within the fjord to that on the shelf (Klinck et al., 1981; Stigebrandt, 1981, 2012; Svendsen, 1980). Density variations are generated by wind convergence and divergence on the shelf, that is, downwelling and upwelling or advection of horizontal density gradients along the coast. In winter months, southerly winds and downwelling conditions have been shown to ultimately develop the Spitsbergen Trough Current (STC), guiding AW onto lower isobaths on the shelf, eventually advecting AW into West Spitsbergen fjords (Nilsen et al., 2016). Similar examples of this “intermediary circulation” have been observed in Kongsfjorden (De Rovere et al., 2024) and in Greenland fjords (Jackson et al., 2014; Straneo et al., 2010). Upwelling, driven by northerly winds blowing over the WSS, is an effective mechanism of lateral transport of WSC waters onto the shelf and fjords (Cottier et al., 2007). Indeed, strong northerly winds force surface waters from the shelf toward the open ocean, which in turn are compensated by an inflow of WSC waters at intermediate and deep layers. Westerly winds and a negative meridional Ekman transport were found to suppress the fresher and colder SPC outflows from the Barents Sea (Goszczko et al., 2018). Other effective means of cross-shelf transport are topographic waves generated by a combination of barotropic and baroclinic instabilities (Inall et al., 2015; Nilsen et al., 2006; Teigen et al., 2010, 2011; Tverberg et al., 2019). Inputs of freshwater into the fjord system, originating from surface melting (Lydersen et al., 2014; Scholzen et al., 2021), enhance along-fjord circulation with subglacial flows from tidewater glaciers (Holmes et al., 2019; Luckman et al., 2015) contributing with buoyancy-driven circulation (Aliani et al., 2004; Ingvaldsen et al., 2001; Straneo & Cenedese, 2015; Sundfjord et al., 2017). Low-salinity meltwaters are forced to exit the fjord due to their lower density than surface waters on the shelf, activating an inflow of deep shelf waters near the bottom due to volume conservation (Stigebrandt, 2012).

Tverberg et al. (2019) described water mass characteristics and seasonality in Kongsfjorden. Summer is the season when pure AW or Transformed Atlantic Water (TAW) occupy a considerable fraction of the fjord volume. A thin layer of surface water (SW) is generated as freshwater is released into the system from glaciers and snow melting. Underneath SW, intermediate water (IW), that is, a mix between water masses of different origin (AW, TAW, LW, and SW), is present. The fjord can also host local water (LW) and Winter Cooled Water (WCW) produced in the previous autumn and winter. Table 1 reports the water masses classification used in this study adapted from Tverberg et al. (2019).

Atlantification in West Spitsbergen fjords is observed as a positive temperature and salinity trend especially in the latter decades (Bloshkina et al., 2021; Cottier et al., 2022; De Rovere et al., 2022; Skogseth et al., 2020; Strzelewicz et al., 2022; Tverberg et al., 2019). In particular, Kongsfjorden (Tverberg et al., 2019) and nearby Isfjorden (Skogseth et al., 2020) shifted after winter 2006 from being typical Arctic fjords with the presence of sea ice and limited or deep inflow of AW to a more Atlantic type fjord characterized by less sea ice and occasional AW advection in the upper part of the water column. As regards Isfjorden, Bloshkina et al. (2021) found significant positive trends in temperature and salinity by examining CTD data acquired in the outer part of the fjord in late summer from 2003 to 2019. Various studies led to some insights into fjord-shelf water exchange mechanisms in this area, but it is yet to be explained which are the main drivers of the observed long-term increasing fraction of AW in summer and associated temperature and salinity positive trends from mid 1990s, even though Tverberg et al. (2019) identified a link with the heat flux on the shelf area.

This study investigates the recent summer hydrographic variability in the fjord as well as in the adjacent shelf and open ocean areas to identify the main drivers explaining the increasing summer presence of AW in Kongsfjorden. We hypothesize that changes in wind patterns and river runoff, by means of the processes described above, may partly explain increased fjord-shelf exchanges, leading to a larger fraction of AW in Kongsfjorden and increasing its heat content (HC). We justify this hypothesis by analyzing hydrographic trends in Kongsfjorden and wind patterns in the surrounding area, and we test the hypothesis with an ocean model. To achieve these goals we

Figure 1. (a) Map of Svalbard archipelago with main fjords and water currents (Atlantic in red and Arctic in blue). Area A1 (purple rectangle) represents the geographical domain examined with NORA3 wind data. (b) Map of Kongsfjorden and the adjacent shelf with locations of CTD stations (KB stations are located in Kongsfjorden, whereas V stations are located on the adjacent shelf and open ocean) and domain of the K160 ocean model (dashed rectangle). The Kapp-Guissez Transect (KGT) is set at the mouth of inner Kongsfjorden. Current arrows are the same as in panel (a). Color shadings represent bathymetry.

Table 1
Water Masses Definitions in Kongsfjorden Adapted From Tverberg et al. (2019)

	Temperature (°C)	Salinity
Atlantic Water	$T \geq 3$	$S \geq 34.9$
Transformed Atlantic Water	$T \geq 1$	$S \geq 34.7$
Surface water	$T \geq 1$	$S \leq 34$
Intermediate water	$T \geq 1$	$34 \leq S \leq 34.7$
Local water	$T \leq 1$	
Winter cooled water	$T \leq 0.5$	$S \geq 34.4$

examine: (a) the interannual evolution of water masses in the fjord and the WSC; (b) the multiannual evolution in temperature, salinity, and density in the fjord and the adjacent shelf and open ocean; (c) the role of wind-driven Ekman transport and river runoff—two key mechanisms influencing shelf-fjord exchanges—in relation to the observed multiannual variability. We combine data analysis of the available CTD profiles with reanalysis data as well as numerical experiments with a high-resolution ocean model (K160).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. CTD Observations and Analysis

The Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) has conducted extensive summer hydrographic surveys in Kongsfjorden and on the adjacent shelf from 1999 to 2020. The locations of the CTD stations are shown in Figure 1b and detailed in Table S1 in Supporting Information S1. The NPI summer CTD data set represents an unique opportunity to compare properties observed in the fjord, on the WSS and in the WSC. CTD data were acquired during summer cruises in Kongsfjorden and on the adjacent shelf and slope as part of the MOSJ (Environmental Monitoring of Svalbard and Jan Mayen) program (<https://www.mosj.no/en/about/>), usually in the second half of July, from 1999 to 2020 except for 2005 (Figure S1 in Supporting Information S1). Three stations were identified as representative of the conditions in the fjord (KB3), the shelf (V12), that is, where the polar front between the WSC and the SPC is usually found, and the continental slope (V10), that is, where the WSC flows. All temperature and salinity profiles were averaged with 1 m resolution in the vertical. KB3 was selected as a reference station representing conditions in Kongsfjorden because of its central position in the fjord and its long data availability. The HC (units: J/m^3) between 10 and 250 m depth was calculated at selected stations using the formula:

$$HC_{\text{station}} = \frac{\int_{h2=250}^{h1=10} \theta \rho C_p dz}{h2 - h1}$$

where $h1$ and $h2$ are the two selected depths, θ is potential temperature, ρ is the potential density, and C_p is the specific heat of seawater. Units are J/m . In this text, we use the terms HC_{KB3} and HC_{V10} to refer to the observed HC in the 10–250 m depth layer from measurements acquired at stations KB3 and V10.

Water masses were categorized following the classification by Tverberg et al. (2019) and adapted to assess water masses in Kongsfjorden and the adjacent shelf. Temperature, salinity, and density trends for the 2002–2020 period, at different depths, averaged at 10 m resolution, are inspected for each station using regression analysis. Bins with more than five missing measures were excluded from the analysis. A correlation analysis (Lee Rodgers & Nicewander, 1988) was conducted to examine the variability in HC_{KB3} and water masses properties.

2.2. Auxiliary Data: Wind and River Runoff

Wind data were obtained from NORA3 (Haakenstad et al., 2021), which is a 3 km resolution, non-hydrostatic model used to downscale ERA5 atmospheric reanalyses (Hersbach et al., 2020), covering the Norwegian Sea and coasts including the Svalbard archipelago. Six-hourly wind fields from NORA3 reanalysis data were evaluated in the geographical domain represented by area A1 (Figure 1a) to describe winds on the WSS. The cumulative summer (June–July–August) eastward ($+M_x$), westward ($-M_x$), northward ($+M_y$), southward ($-M_y$) surface Ekman transports, as well as the surface wind stress (τ) over the WSS, were calculated using the daily averaged winds over area A1 by Goszczko et al. (2018). Freshwater runoff from glaciers in Kongsfjorden is from a model simulating the energy balance of the glaciers, the meltwater fluxes, and their routing into the fjord (van Pelt et al., 2019). We calculated the total summer river runoff volume in Kongsfjorden (RR_{tot}), the starting and end dates of river runoff fluxes with different magnitudes (greater than 20, 40, and 60 m^3/s) as well as the total number of days per year featuring such fluxes. A linear trend analysis on the auxiliary variables was implemented to detect any temporal change linked with HC_{KB3} evolution through mechanisms described in the literature. A correlation analysis was conducted between the HC_{KB3} and auxiliary variables using the Pearson coefficient. We use 0.05 as the significance level in all statistical analyses.

2.3. K160 Model and Idealized Experiments

2.3.1. Model Description

The present model simulations are based on a nested model system described by Sundfjord et al. (2017), comprising a 4-km horizontal resolution pan-Arctic model domain (A4), an 800-m resolution Svalbard domain (S800), and a Kongsfjorden domain with 160 m resolution (K160). All models were implemented with the Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS, Shchepetkin & McWilliams, 2005). Daily averages from the A4 model are used to provide open boundary conditions for the S800 model domain, and tidal forcing for both A4 and S800 is provided by the global TPXO v7.2 model (Egbert & Erofeeva, 2002). Hourly output from S800 is used to define boundary conditions for the K160 model, hence the inner nested layer did not make use of a separate tidal model. Fjord simulations were carried out after a 9-month spin-up period (September 2006–May 2007), followed by a 4-month simulation period (June–September 2007). The settings of the K160 model, including the extent of the model domain, horizontal resolution (160 m), number of vertical topography-following levels (35) and bathymetry are the same as described by Torsvik et al. (2019) except for the differences listed in the next paragraphs.

We use a different parametrization for subglacial discharge plumes. Torsvik et al. (2019) used a subglacial discharge profile based on a bell-shaped curve comprising five vertical grid cells, whose maximum discharge was five grid cells above the seabed (Figure 2b in Torsvik et al. (2019)), implying that the discharge depth depends on the water depth at each tidewater glacier terminus. Results obtained by Torsvik et al. (2019) comparing inflows to the river cells, obtained from the ocean model and used as a proxy of entrainment of ambient seawater into the plume, with entrainment rates calculated with the 1D plume analytical model *pyplume* (Everett et al., 2018), suggest that the former may have a positive bias (Figure S3 in Torsvik et al. (2019)). We use the approach developed by Cowton et al. (2015) and implemented by Wang (2019) in ROMS (available at <https://github.com/ChuningWang/roms-iceplume>), which is based on the coupling of an analytical plume model with the ocean circulation model. The former calculates the vertical movement of water and tracers at each time step at a specified location within the ocean model, eliminating the need to resolve the glacial plume and permitting much coarser model resolution. This has the advantage of greatly reducing the simulation time while still allowing the plume to evolve as subglacial discharge or conditions in the fjord change. Water, heat, salt, and other tracers are then removed from the ocean model cells at the rate predicted by the plume model in those vertical layers where the plume is entraining and put into the cell at the depth at which the plume is predicted to terminate. Freshwater runoff is derived from SnowModel (Liston & Elder, 2006) for the period 1961–2012 (Van Pelt and Kohler, 2015).

We use spatially variable Jerlov water types defined in the ROMS grid file (Figure S2 in Supporting Information S1) based on light extinction data from Gattuso et al. (2020). This allows us to take into account the increasing turbidity from the shelf toward the glacier fronts, which affects the ocean radiation balance and hence the uptake and distribution of heat.

The high-resolution atmospheric fields used to force the fjord models are from the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF) developed by the National Center of Atmospheric Research (NCAR). The WRF model is a state-of-the-art numerical weather prediction model (Skamarock et al., 2008), and the implementation of the WRF model included a domain with horizontal grid resolution of 3 km. The model was initialized with an analysis (on a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid) from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), and lateral boundary values were updated every sixth hour during integration. Turbulent fluxes in ROMS (momentum, heat, and freshwater) are calculated interactively using ROMS sea surface temperature and WRF atmospheric data by applying the Coupled Ocean Atmosphere Response Experiment (COARE) algorithm (Fairall et al., 2003).

2.3.2. Model Evaluation

A base simulation (Sim0) was run for summer 2007 and the output compared with more than 300 CTD profiles collected in the period 1 June–1 October 2007 (Skogseth et al., 2019) for model evaluation (Figure S3 in Supporting Information S1). This comparison shows that the model reproduces relatively well the water column stratification, and that salinity and temperature biases have a large spatial variability. We analyzed the reasons for these biases and concluded that they are due mostly to the boundary conditions from the S800 model (cf. 2.4.1). Taylor diagrams (Taylor, 2001) show a large improvement in the performance of the K160 model when compared to the model in which it is nested (S800): (a) the centered root mean square difference for salinity (Figure S4a in Supporting Information S1) and for temperature (Figure S4b in Supporting Information S1) was reduced from

~1.5 to ~0.5 and from ~1.3°C to ~1.0°C, respectively; (b) the correlation coefficients for salinity and for temperature increased from ~0.6 to ~0.9 and from ~0.3 to ~0.5, respectively; (c) the standard deviation became closer to that of the observations for salinity, whereas for temperature, there was not any considerable change. Note that within the framework of our sensitivity experiments (see Section 2.4.3), even though the model behaves satisfactorily, the response to the different imposed scenarios is more important than the accuracy.

2.3.3. Model Simulations

We performed four simulations (Sim1, Sim2, Sim3, and Sim4) to test the importance of potential drivers of the fjord's HC. These experiments were defined following the results of the CTD (Section 3.1) and auxiliary (Section 3.2) data analysis and will be further justified in the Discussion (Section 4.2). Each scenario reflects changes in Sim0 regarding one specific model forcing to recreate conditions hypothesized to act as drivers of the HC in the fjord. The modified forcing for Sim1 and Sim4 reproduces patterns observed in years when upwelling conditions on the WSS and river flows were stronger. Both upwelling (Cottier et al., 2007) and river runoff (Stigebrandt, 2012; Straneo & Cenedese, 2015; Sundfjord et al., 2017) may enhance intermediary circulation and force inflows of shelf bottom waters into the fjord. However, Sim1 differs from Sim0 in both wind direction (WD) and wind speed (WS). Therefore, Sim2 and Sim3 were performed to disentangle the role of these two variables in the differences between Sim0 and Sim1. The following points describe each scenario specifically its changes compared to Sim0:

- Sim1. K160 is coupled with the NORA3 wind field for summer 2015, which is the one with the largest $-M_x$ (see Section 3.2). The NORA3 wind fields were bilinearly interpolated onto the K160 grid.
- Sim2. This scenario examines the consequences of changing WD only. Zonal (u) and meridional (v) winds from Sim1 were rescaled so that the WS at each time step and geographical location is equal to the corresponding WS of Sim0. Scaling was performed as follows. For each location and time step, u and v have the following relation:

$$v = X \cdot u$$

where X is a scaling factor. Our target is to retain the X observed in Sim1 but prescribe the same WS as Sim0. Thus, using the above relation and the wind speed equation, we prescribe the WS for Sim2:

$$WS_{Sim2} = WS_{Sim0} = \sqrt{u_{Sim2}^2 + (X_{Sim1} \cdot u_{Sim2})^2}$$

And then find u_{Sim2} and v_{Sim2} :

$$u_{Sim2} = \sqrt{\frac{WS_{Sim0}^2}{X_{Sim1}^2 + 1}}$$

$$v_{Sim2} = X_{Sim1} \cdot u_{Sim2}$$

In this method, X does not retain the information about the signs of u and v . Hence, we multiply u_{Sim2} and v_{Sim2} by $+1$ or -1 according to the sign of u_{Sim1} and v_{Sim1} . When $u_{Sim1} = 0$, then X_{Sim1} is undetermined. Hence in this case, we prescribed $u_{Sim2} = u_{Sim1} = 0$ and $v_{Sim2} = WS_{Sim0}$.

- Sim3. This scenario examines the consequences of a changing WS only. We followed the same scaling method described above to impose Sim1 WS but retaining Sim0 WD.
- Sim4. K160 is forced with the river runoff output for summer 2016, which is the one with the largest discharged volume and earliest starting date (see Section 3.2).

Model experiments are analyzed by computing the summer average HC in the whole fjord and at KB3. In addition, heat, volume, and AW inflows across KGT toward the fjord over the whole summer are examined. Water masses fractions and associated HCs over summer in the whole fjord, that is, in the area encircled by the Kapp-Guissez transect (KGT) at the fjord entrance (Figure 1b) and land, are reported.

Figure 2. CTD results from station KB3 inside Kongsfjorden (refer to Figure 1b for its geographical location). (a) Summer HC_{KB3} (heat content at KB3 over the 10–250 m depth layer, see Section 2.1). The dashed line identifies a statistically significant trend at the 0.05 confidence level over the 2002–2020 time period. (b) T - S diagram of profiles from 2002 to 2020. (c) Water masses vertical distribution (see Table 1 for water masses classification).

3. Results

3.1. Analysis of CTD Data

The HC_{KB3} over the 10–250 m depth layer in Kongsfjorden, represented by data from KB3, increased significantly between 2002 and 2020 (0.351 MJ/m^3 per year, p -value = 0.038), that is, the common observing period shared with V10, with a minimum and a maximum in 2010 and 2014, respectively (Figure 2a). Considering the whole observed period at KB3 (from 1999 to 2020), the positive trend is still statistically significant (0.44 MJ/m^3 per year, p -value = 0.001). The T - S diagram in Figure 2b indicates that more recent years (yellow and orange colors) are characterized by higher temperatures and salinities. There are always layers of AW and/or TAW, under the IW, except for the year 2000 (Figure 2c). Furthermore, there is always a surface layer of low-density SW over a layer of IW, which rarely exceeds 150 m depth. The period of study features a decreasing presence of LW and an increasing influence of TAW and AW, the latter especially from 2014.

No significant summer trend (-0.02 MJ/m^3 per year, p -value = 0.817) was observed for HC_{V10} (Figure 3a). Years 2007 and 2017 are the ones with larger HC_{V10} , whereas 2010 exhibits the lowest value. HC_{KB3} and HC_{V10} have the lowest value in the same year, whereas there is not a temporal match between the two stations for the highest HC values. V10 has a lower multiannual variability in water properties compared to the fjord. Here, early and late years of the observed period do not diverge as much as inside the fjord (Figure 3b). The water column at station V10 is almost entirely occupied by AW, suggesting that this station can be considered representative of WSC properties at the upper continental slope (Figure 3c). Station V10 is positioned at the shelf edge, a location with a sharp bathymetric gradient, which explains the large bottom depth variability among the different surveys.

The same analysis was conducted on the other CTD stations, that is, KB5, KB2, KB1, KB0, V12, and V6 (refer to Figure 1b for their geographical positions), and results are reported in Figures S5–S10 in Supporting Information S1. Observations at KB3 are consistent with the other stations located in the fjord (KB5, KB2, KB1, and KB0) pointing to a significant increase in Kongsfjorden's HC over the study period. Similarly, stations V12 and V6 mirror the evolution of V10 with a stable HC.

Figure 3. CTD results from station V10 outside Kongsfjorden (refer to Figure 1b for its geographical location). (a) Summer HC_{V10} (heat content at V10 over the 10–250 m depth layer, see Section 2.1); (b) T - S diagram of profiles from 2002 to 2020; (c) water masses vertical distribution (see Table 1 for water masses classification).

Stations representing the WSC (V10 and V6) do not show significant temperature trends (Figures 4a and 4b). The station on the shelf (V12) shows a positive temperature trend only in the shallowest layers of the water column (Figure 4c). On the contrary, temperature shows a similar behavior among stations located within the fjord (from KB0 to KB3) with significant positive trends in the central and lower part of the water column (Figures 4d–4g). Salinity shows a similar pattern compared to temperature. The continental slope (V10) and open ocean (V6) stations do not show a significant change (Figures 4i and 4j). Significant positive trends are present in the fjord (KB0, KB1, KB2, and KB3 stations), especially in the intermediate and near-bottom layers of the water column (Figures 4l–4o). Potential density does not exhibit significant trends at any of the examined stations. Results from Figure 4 are another clear indication of the different characteristics in Kongsfjorden, the proximal shelf, and the WSC.

The increasing HC_{KB3} was considered in relation with the volume and “purity” of Atlantic waters in the fjord. A correlation analysis between HC_{KB3} in the 10–200 m depth layer and average salinity and volume fraction of the AW and TAW layers was performed. Here, salinity is used as a proxy for the purity of Atlantic waters. Both salinity and volume fraction show a significant correlation with HC_{KB3} with coefficients measuring 0.81 and 0.87, respectively (Figure S11 in Supporting Information S1). Furthermore, the difference in temperature and salinity between the fjord (KB3) and the continental slope (V10) decreases significantly (Figure S12 in Supporting Information S1).

3.2. Analysis of Auxiliary Data

The summer wind field in the area of study is examined over the period 1999–2020, where HC_{KB3} is exhibiting a significant positive change. Considerable interannual and long-term variability is present over this period. $-M_x$ exhibits the highest cumulative values among all Ekman transport components for almost every summer (Figure 5b). Only $-M_x$ shows a statistically significant trend ($2 \times 10^{-4} m^2/s$ per year) during the 1999–2020 period (Figures 5a–5d). The observed increase in $-M_x$ points to an increasing upwelling activity over the fjord and its adjacent shelf, which may enhance the inflow of AW into the fjord. Furthermore, τ in area A1 is significantly increasing over the period of study ($4.4 \times 10^{-5} N^2/m$ per year), resulting in several continuous summers with large surface wind stress especially from 2008 onwards (Figure 5e).

Figure 4. (a–h) Linear trend coefficients for potential temperature, (i–p) salinity, and (q–x) potential density over 10 m bins across stations considered in this study. Red and cyan dots represent positive and negative significant trend coefficients ($p < 0.05$), respectively.

The total river runoff in Kongsfjorden has shown a notable increase during the period 2006–2017 (0.02 km^3 per year) with 2016 being the year with the largest value (Figure 6a). An analysis of freshwater fluxes with three different magnitudes reveals significant trends in the onset date of >40 and $>60 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ fluxes, shifting from late June to early June (Figure 6b) and an advancement in the offset date, moving from late August/early September to mid and late September (Figure 6c). Consequently, the duration of the freshwater discharge period has extended throughout the study period for all considered fluxes (Figure 6d). This increase in both the total volume and the duration of freshwater discharge enhances the circulation driven by surface runoff and corresponding horizontal density gradients. Significant correlations were identified only between the starting dates of river runoff for the various fluxes and HC_{KB3} .

Results indicate three significant temporal changes acting in the direction of increased fjord-shelf exchanges and AW inflows in Kongsfjorden: strengthening northerly winds enhancing upwelling on the WSS, strengthening wind stress over the WSS, amplified freshwater runoff volume and duration in the fjord. These results motivated the design and performance of the model experiments described in Section 2.3.3 to assess the impact of such changes on the hydrography of the fjord.

3.3. Model Results

Simulation scenarios were defined from the results described in Section 3.2. Scenarios are either based on specific years when $-M_x$ and river runoff were more prominent (Sim1 and Sim4) or help disentangle the roles of changes in WD and WS.

We first describe the results of Sim1 and Sim4. Sustained conditions of strong westward Ekman transport had the most significant impact on the fjord's HC (Figure 7a). Profiles of temperature deviation from Sim0 at KB3

Figure 5. Summer cumulative Ekman transports calculated from the average NORA3 10 m wind field over area A1: (a) $+M_x$, (b) $-M_x$, (c) $+M_y$, and (d) $-M_y$. (e) Summer cumulative τ calculated from the average wind over area A1. Trends are computed over the 1999–2020 time period. Dashed lines identify statistically significant trends at the 0.05 confidence level.

indicate warming in both the mid and lower sections of the water column for both scenarios (not shown). Summer average HC in the 10–250 m depth layer at KB3 reflects variations in the total fjord HC (Figure 7b). Sim1 and Sim4 led to increases in both the volume (Figure 7c) and heat (Figure 7d) inflow to the fjord over the entire summer by 15% and 5%, respectively. The inflow of AW was boosted by approximately 25% in Sim1 and 10% in Sim4 (Figure 7e). The average AW fraction within the fjord rose by nearly 12% in Sim1 and 6% in Sim4 (Figure 7f), whereas there was a notable decrease in the average TAW fraction over summer (Figure 7g). The IW fraction remained relatively stable in Sim1 but decreased by 8% in Sim4 (Figure 7h). The SW fraction experiences a slight increase in both scenarios rising by 5.5% in Sim1 and almost 8% in Sim4 (Figure 7i). The average HC for each specific water mass shows insignificant changes except for TAW, which increases by 8% in Sim1 and 6% in Sim4 (Figures 7j–7m).

Sim2 and Sim3 help disentangle the confounding effects of WS and WD, when contrasting Sim1 with Sim0. Sim2 generated a clear change in fjord's conditions by augmenting the fjord HC, whereas no significant changes are seen for Sim3 (Figure 7a). However, Sim2 and Sim3 did not substantially modify inflows of volume, heat, and AW into the fjord compared to Sim0 (Figures 7c–7e). Water masses' fractions in Sim2 appeared to deviate from Sim0 with AW and TAW volumes significantly less than Sim1 and comparable to those characterizing Sim3 and Sim4 (Figures 7f and 7g). No major change in the AW HC was observed in Sim2 compared to Sim0 and Sim1, whereas Sim3 showed a considerable decrease (Figure 7j). Sim2 featured the largest HCs for IW and SW among all scenarios (Figures 7l and 7m).

Figure 6. Meltwater runoff from glaciers in Kongsfjorden. (a) Total summer runoff from all glaciers in Kongsfjorden. (b) Melt onset date, (c) melt end date, and (d) number of days with glacier runoff. Colors in panels (b–d) identify runoff fluxes with varying minimum intensities: $>20 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (green), $>40 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (orange), and $>60 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (purple). Dashed lines identify significant linear trends at the 0.05 confidence level.

The net heat transport toward Kongsfjorden was primarily influenced by the volume transport in all scenarios. In Sim0, water and heat inflows were observed in the central part of the KGT transect, extending from the near-surface down to approximately 230 m depth (Figures 8a and 8d). Additionally, inflows occurred along the southern side of the fjord at mid-depth and near the bottom. Outflows of water and heat were present along the northern side of the fjord, occurring from 50 m depth to the bottom, as well as near the surface on the southern side. Sim1 showed pronounced inflowing anomalies along the southern side and significant outflowing anomalies along the northern side of Kongsfjorden. Under conditions of enhanced river runoff (Sim4), positive volume and heat transport anomalies were concentrated in the mid-fjord region, from the near-surface to 200 m depth, as well as along the southern side of the fjord, both near the surface and at mid-depths (Figures 8c and 8f). Conversely, moderate negative anomalies characterized the deep fjord and the near-surface to mid-depths along the northern side.

4. Discussion

We discuss the results as follows. First, the HCs and temperature trends in Kongsfjorden are considered in relation to the fractions of the different water masses (Section 4.1). Next, conditions that facilitate the intrusions of warm water into the fjord during summer are examined (Section 4.2).

4.1. Evolution of Summer Water Properties in Kongsfjorden

HC_{KB3} , temperature, and salinity in Kongsfjorden have been increasing between 1999 and 2020. Warming and salinification take place especially in the intermediate and deeper part of the water column. These trends are primarily explained by an increase in the volume fraction and purity of AW in the fjord. Since WSC waters are typically warmer and saltier than fjord waters, we argue that marine conditions in the fjord in this time frame became more similar to those in the WSC. This is supported also by the decreasing temperature and salinity

Figure 7. Results of model scenario analysis: (a) summer average heat content (HC) in Kongsfjorden; (b) summer average HC at KB3 in the 10–250 m depth layer, expressed in MJ/m³ for comparison with Figure 2; inflow of (c) water, (d) heat, and (e) AW over summer; (f–i) average volume fraction of AW, TAW, IW, and SW in Kongsfjorden; (j–m) average HC per m³ of AW, TAW, IW, and SW. Almost null fractions of LW and WCW are found in the fjord. Axes on the right side in all panels report the anomaly relative to Sim0 in terms of percentage change.

differences between the fjord and the continental slope, suggesting that AW summer intrusions in Kongsfjorden have become more extensive. Even though other studies found increasing WSC temperatures in different time periods from multiannual to multidecadal timescales (Beszczynska-Möller et al., 2012; Pavlov et al., 2013; Tesi

Figure 8. (a) Summer average heat and (d) volume net fluxes toward Kongsfjorden across KGT (see Figure 1b for transect's location) for Sim0. Positive values indicate fluxes directed toward the inner fjord. Summer average heat and volume net flux anomalies toward Kongsfjorden compared to Sim0 for (b, e) Sim1 and (c, f) Sim4.

et al., 2021), our CTD data do not show a warming between 2002 and 2020. Therefore, we propose that the larger HC in Kongsfjorden is primarily related to larger intrusions of AW and not to a change in the upstream WSC properties. Summer temperature and salinity trends observed in Kongsfjorden agree with those observed in Isfjorden in 2003–2016 by Bloskhina et al. (2021) (Table S2 in Supporting Information S1). Therefore, we speculate that these trends may also be primarily related to an increasing fraction of AW.

4.2. Contributions to Larger AW Intrusions in Kongsfjorden

Here, we investigate the role of westward Ekman transport and river runoff in the augmented HC in Kongsfjorden. In line with the reasoning developed in Section 4.1, the drivers of the positive HC trend are those leading to a higher fraction of AW especially in the intermediate and near-bottom layers and exhibiting temporal trends consistent with the increase in AW intrusions.

Northerly winds on the WSS generate a westward surface Ekman transport and upwelling, uplifting AW from the core of the WSC onto the shelf (Cottier et al., 2007), and developing intermediary circulation and shelf-fjord exchanges (Stigebrandt, 1981, 2012). Our results showed that $-M_x$ increased over 1999–2020 and model results confirm that a larger cumulative $-M_x$ lead to enhanced HC in the fjord over summer. The increase in HC and temperature, especially in the intermediate and bottom layers, was due to the presence of more AW and not due to an increase in its HC. Sim1 reveals that strong offshore Ekman transport, driven by northerly winds, significantly alters the flow patterns through KGT in Sim0. In particular, the inflow is enhanced in the southern half of the transect, whereas the outflow is stronger in the northern half. A two-layer flow, that is, outflows at the near-surface and inflows along the intermediate and bottom layers, is characteristic of intermediary circulation at the fjord mouth (Stigebrandt, 2012). However, anomalous inflows and outflows do not seem to be varying with depth in Sim1, thus questioning our initial hypothesis of a strengthened intermediary circulation explaining the observed increase in fjord HC. To solve this issue, we verify whether the anomalous volume inflow observed in Sim1 (relative to Sim0) is accounted by the anomalous “theoretical” volume transport that would be generated by the wind observed in 2015 (relative to 2007). Assuming that the zonal surface outflows forced by winds approximately match the compensating inflows along the intermediate and bottom layers, one can roughly calculate the volume inflow in Kongsfjorden by multiplying the zonal surface Ekman transport over summer (the sum of $+M_x$ and $-M_x$ as reported in Figure 5) to the length of KGT (approximately 12 km). Our calculation

Figure 9. Depth-averaged temperature (color maps) and transport (arrows) difference between Sim1 and Sim0 in the (a, b) near-surface layer (0–70 m depth) and in the (c, d) intermediate and bottom layers (70–400 m depth). The left column reports data for the fjord and shelf, whereas the right column shows data for the fjord only. Arrows report depth-averaged transports averaged within 1 km distance from each arrow base.

indicates that the anomalous volume inflow in Sim1 is 4 times larger than the anomalous “theoretical” volume inflow, suggesting that the enhanced volume exchanges observed in Sim1 are not only due to changes in zonal Ekman transport. Hence, we better investigate what other processes are concurring to the enhanced volume inflow in Sim1 by assessing the horizontal depth-averaged transports in the area of study reported in Figure 9.

Results clearly show the development of two different anomalous eddy-like circulations; an anticyclonic one at the mid-shelf (Figures 9a–9c) and a cyclonic one at the fjord entrance (Figures 9b and 9d). Interestingly, these patterns characterize the whole water column but appear more intense near the surface likely because of the enhanced northerly wind stress in Sim1. The anomalous horizontal pattern at the fjord entrance agrees with the cross-vertical pattern observed in Figure 8 with strong anomalous inflows (outflows) along the southern (northern) shore. We thus suggest that the augmented volume, heat, and AW inflow in Sim1 is not principally linked to the establishment of intermediary circulation but to the development of significant changes in the horizontal transport at the fjord mouth and on the shelf. The establishment of eddy-like anomalous circulation throughout the whole water column on the shelf indicates that changes in the wind field largely influence the barotropic field resulting in larger inflows of shelf waters into the fjord.

Besides $-M_x$, τ is significantly increasing in area A1 over the period of study. This may be attributed to either the increase in $-M_x$ or the influence of more dynamic atmospheric conditions over Western Spitsbergen, the latter contributing to the development of barotropic/baroclinic instabilities and topographic waves (Inall et al., 2015; Nilsen et al., 2006; Teigen et al., 2010, 2011) or the suppression of the SPC transport along the WSS (Goszczko et al., 2018). However, again, only $-M_x$ shows a significant increase over the study period. Thus, what is the

relative importance of changes in τ compared to changes in $-M_x$? In other words, what is the relative role of modifications in WS and WD in driving the observed hydrographic changes in Kongsfjorden? To answer this question, we evaluated two scenarios, Sim2 and Sim3, where we prescribed only Sim1 WD and only Sim1 WS, respectively. Results show that modifying WD but retaining WS from Sim0 has a considerable impact on fjord's hydrography, whereas only modifying WS does not generate significant changes compared to the base scenario. This result further corroborates that more common northerly winds in summer help shaping the recent multi-annual hydrographic conditions in the fjord.

The runoffs in Kongsfjorden increased significantly over the observed period, which is expected to enhance horizontal density gradients and the advection of AW into Kongsfjorden. Furthermore, the starting and end dates of river runoff shifted earlier (beginning of June) and later (end of September), respectively. An earlier start of glacier river runoff may activate this circulation earlier leading to AW inflows beforehand in the fjord and larger HCs over summer. Sim4 confirms that a stronger and ahead of time river runoff drives a larger HC in the fjord compared to Sim0. This is mainly caused by the presence of a larger fraction of AW occupying the fjord as well as a warmer TAW. However, results indicate that changes due to enhanced river runoff are smaller than those due to stronger northerly winds. This study did not separately examine the effects of an increasing magnitude and the temporal variations of the outflow. An experimental approach might involve the prescription of a constant river flow over summer while extending the outflow window. However, this setup would not accurately represent real-world conditions.

Despite the consistent temporal trends in $-M_x$, runoff magnitudes, and starting/end dates, we found no significant correlations between these factors and HC_{KB3} . This suggests that interannual changes in these factors do not necessarily covary with HC_{KB3} , but it does not falsify the existence of cause-effect relationships between them. HC_{KB3} in a given year is a result of the interplay between multiple components of the system and one may expect the relative role of such components to vary among different years. This is why we used model experiments, which allow us to disentangle the effects of specific processes. Our findings demonstrate that when other factors are held constant, a summer characterized by elevated $-M_x$ or increased summer river outflow results in greater heat inflow and a higher average summer HC in Kongsfjorden. This, combined with the increasing temporal trends in $-M_x$ and river outflow, provides support to our hypothesis. On the other hand, we found a statistically significant correlation between τ and the HC_{KB3} (0.48, p -value = 0.03). This suggests that the increasing wind stress over the WSS is linked to the long-term summer tendency of the fjord hydrography. However, it contradicts the results of our experiments, where we showed a fjord hydrography more susceptible to changes in WD than WS. We cannot give a definitive explanation to this conflict other than the fact that the wind stress intensity itself is an indicator for different processes, which may shape the fjord hydrography in different ways. Nevertheless, $-M_x$ has the largest summer cumulative absolute values among all components for almost all considered years, hence weighing the most in the τ magnitude.

5. Summary and Conclusions

To the best of our knowledge, this study marks the first attempt to analyse concomitant CTD observations to separately evaluate conditions in Kongsfjorden, the WSS, and the WSC. We achieved this by examining physical measurements performed during MOSJ summer cruises in the fjord, the adjacent shelf, continental slope, and open ocean between 1999 and 2020. The fjord's HC has increased over summer in the study period. Summer temperature and salinity display positive trends in the mid and lower part of the water column. On the other hand, no such trends are observed on the shelf and in the open ocean, where the SPC and WSC flow. Furthermore, the observed increasing HC in the mid-fjord is significantly correlated to larger inflowing volume and purity of AW but not to an overall increase in the AW temperature. Based on this evidence, we conclude that warming and salinification in the fjord are not due to a change in the properties of the upstream Atlantic current but rather to enhanced advection of AW toward the fjord linked to concurrent modifications in environmental parameters leading to enhanced shelf-fjord exchanges. Observed temperature and salinity trends are consistent with those found in Isfjorden, hinting at the occurrence of the same process in fjords facing the WSS.

Three important factors have the potential to enhance shelf-fjord exchanges and a larger AW advection toward Kongsfjorden without modifying the AW properties: larger AW volumes present in front of Kongsfjorden, wind, and river runoff conditions. We tested the latter two and found evidence for significant changes in the summer cumulative westward Ekman transport over the WSS, that is, an indirect measure of upwelling over the shelf, and

the total discharged volume and length of the discharging period in Kongsfjorden. Both changes act toward enhanced shelf-fjord exchanges: although the former enhances upwelling of AW on the WSS, the latter strengthens horizontal density gradients. Simulations indicate that both factors increase the inflow of heat and AW volume in the fjord and contribute to a larger summer HC in the fjord. Among the two, enhanced northerly winds play the most important role by significantly impacting the fjord's local circulation. Regarding modifications in the wind field, changes in the direction (especially the strengthening of northerly winds) have a larger impact on the fjord hydrography compared to changes in the overall velocity. However, our results also show that the increase of HCs resulting from changes in the wind field and river runoff explain but a small part of the changes in HCs observed during the period of study. Therefore, we speculate that the availability of AW on the shelf plays the dominant role.

Data Availability Statement

NPI CTD data (Marnela et al., 2024; Skogseth et al., 2019) are available at the Norwegian Polar Data Centre (<https://data.npolar.no/dataset>) at <https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2019.074A215C> and <https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2024.7414766F>. NORA3 reanalysis data have been downloaded from the THREDDS portal of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (<https://thredds.met.no/thredds/projects/nora3.html>). Glacier runoff data for the 2006–2017 period are available upon request to the authors of Van Pelt and Kohler (2015). K160 model outputs used to plot Figures 7–9 are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15213826>.

References

- Aliani, S., Bartholini, G., Degl'Innocenti, F., Delfanti, R., Galli, C., Lazzoni, E., et al. (2004). Multidisciplinary investigations in the marine environment of the inner Kongsfjord, Svalbard islands (September 2000 and 2001). *Chemistry and Ecology*, 20(sup1), S19–S28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02757540410001655396>
- Andersen, J. K., Andreassen, L. M., Baker, E. H., Ballinger, T. J., Berner, L. T., Bernhard, G. H., et al. (2020). The Arctic. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 101(8), S239–S286. <https://doi.org/10.1175/bams-d-20-0086.1>
- Årthun, M., Eldevik, T., Smedsrud, L. H., Skagseth, Ø., & Ingvaldsen, R. B. (2012). Quantifying the influence of Atlantic heat on Barents Sea ice variability and retreat. *Journal of Climate*, 25(13), 4736–4743. <https://doi.org/10.1175/jcli-d-11-00466.1>
- Beszczynska-Möller, A., Fahrback, E., Schauer, U., & Hansen, E. (2012). Variability in Atlantic Water temperature and transport at the entrance to the Arctic Ocean, 1997–2010. *ICES Journal of Marine Science: Journal Du Conseil*, 69(5), 852–863. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fss056>
- Bloshkina, E. V., Pavlov, A. K., & Filchuk, K. (2021). Warming of Atlantic water in three West Spitsbergen fjords: Recent patterns and century-long trends. *Polar Research*, 40. <https://doi.org/10.33265/polar.v40.5392>
- Cottier, F., Skogseth, R., David, D., De Rovere, F., Vogedes, D., Daase, M., & Berge, J. (2022). Temperature and salinity time series in Svalbard fjords – ‘Integrated Marine Observatory Partnership (iMOP II)’. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5751717>
- Cottier, F. R., Nilsen, F., Inall, M. E., Gerland, S., Tverberg, V., & Svendsen, H. (2007). Wintertime warming of an Arctic shelf in response to large-scale atmospheric circulation. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 34(10), L10607. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007gl029948>
- Cowton, T., Slater, D., Sole, A., Goldberg, D., & Nienow, P. (2015). Modeling the impact of glacial runoff on fjord circulation and submarine melt rate using a new subgrid-scale parameterization for glacial plumes. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 120(2), 796–812. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014jc010324>
- De Rovere, F., Langone, L., Schroeder, K., Miserocchi, S., Giglio, F., Aliani, S., & Chiggiato, J. (2022). Water masses variability in inner Kongsfjorden (Svalbard) during 2010–2020. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 741075. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.741075>
- De Rovere, F., Zanchettin, D., Rubino, A., Langone, L., Calogiuri, F., Ruggieri, P., et al. (2024). Winter intrusions of Atlantic Water in Kongsfjorden: Oceanic preconditioning and atmospheric triggering. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 129(7), e2023JC020095. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023jc020095>
- Egbert, G. D., & Erofeeva, S. Y. (2002). Efficient inverse modeling of barotropic ocean tides. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 19(2), 183–204. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0426\(2002\)019<0183:eimobo>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0426(2002)019<0183:eimobo>2.0.co;2)
- Everett, A., Kohler, J., Sundfjord, A., Kovacs, K. M., Torsvik, T., Pramanik, A., et al. (2018). Subglacial discharge plume behaviour revealed by CTD-instrumented ringed seals. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-31875-8>
- Fairall, C. W., Bradley, E. F., Hare, J. E., Grachev, A. A., & Edson, J. B. (2003). Bulk parameterization of air–sea fluxes: Updates and verification for the COARE algorithm. *Journal of Climate*, 16(4), 571–591. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(2003\)016<0571:bpoasf>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2003)016<0571:bpoasf>2.0.co;2)
- Gattuso, J.-P., Gentili, B., Antoine, D., & Doxaran, D. (2020). Global distribution of photosynthetically available radiation on the seafloor. *Earth System Science Data*, 12(3), 1697–1709. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-1697-2020>
- Goszczko, I., Ingvaldsen, R. B., & Onarheim, I. H. (2018). Wind-driven cross-shelf exchange—West Spitsbergen current as a source of heat and salt for the adjacent shelf in Arctic winters. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 123(4), 2668–2696. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017jc013553>
- Haakenstad, H., Breivik, Ø., Furevik, B. R., Reistad, M., Bohlinger, P., & Aarnes, O. J. (2021). NORA3: A nonhydrostatic high-resolution hindcast of the North Sea, the Norwegian Sea, and the Barents Sea. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 60(10), 1443–1464. <https://doi.org/10.1175/jamc-d-21-0029.1>
- Helland-Hansen, B., & Nansen, F. (1909). The Norwegian Sea: Its physical oceanography based upon the Norwegian researches 1900–1904. Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Hirahara, S., Horányi, A., Muñoz-Sabater, J., et al. (2020). The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 146(730), 1999–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>
- Holmes, F. A., Kirchner, N., Kutteneuler, J., Krützfeldt, J., & Noormets, R. (2019). Relating ocean temperatures to frontal ablation rates at Svalbard tidewater glaciers: Insights from glacier proximal datasets. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45077-3>

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- Inall, M. E., Nilsen, F., Cottier, F. R., & Daae, R. (2015). Shelf/fjord exchange driven by coastal-trapped waves in the Arctic. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 120(12), 8283–8303. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015jc011277>
- Ingvaldsen, R., Reitan, M. B., Svendsen, H., & Asplin, L. (2001). The upper layer circulation in Kongsfjorden and Krossfjorden—A complex fjord system on the west coast of Spitsbergen.
- Jackson, R. H., Straneo, F., & Sutherland, D. A. (2014). Externally forced fluctuations in ocean temperature at Greenland glaciers in non-summer months. *Nature Geoscience*, 7(7), 503–508. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2186>
- Klinck, J. M., O'Brien, J. J., & Svendsen, H. (1981). A simple model of fjord and coastal circulation interaction. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 11(12), 1612–1626. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1981\)011<1612:asmofa>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1981)011<1612:asmofa>2.0.co;2)
- Lee Rodgers, J., & Nicewander, W. A. (1988). Thirteen ways to look at the correlation coefficient. *The American Statistician*, 42(1), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.1988.10475524>
- Lind, S., Ingvaldsen, R. B., & Furevik, T. (2018). Arctic warming hotspot in the northern Barents Sea linked to declining sea-ice import. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(7), 634–639. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0205-y>
- Liston, G. E., & Elder, K. (2006). A distributed snow-evolution modeling system (SnowModel). *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, 7(6), 1259–1276. <https://doi.org/10.1175/jhm548.1>
- Luckman, A., Benn, D. I., Cottier, F., Bevan, S., Nilsen, F., & Inall, M. (2015). Calving rates at tidewater glaciers vary strongly with ocean temperature. *Nature Communications*, 6(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms9566>
- Lydersen, C., Assmy, P., Falk-Petersen, S., Kohler, J., Kovacs, K. M., Reigstad, M., et al. (2014). The importance of tidewater glaciers for marine mammals and seabirds in Svalbard, Norway. *Journal of Marine Systems: Journal of the European Association of Marine Sciences and Techniques*, 129, 452–471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2013.09.006>
- Marnela, M., Assmy, P., Bailey, A., Daase, M., Divine, D., Duarte, P., et al. (2024). CTD profiles with auxiliary sensors from Kongsfjorden and Rijpfjorden cruises in 2011–2020 [Dataset]. *Norwegian Polar Institute*. <https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2024.7414766F>
- Nilsen, F., Gjevik, B., & Schauer, U. (2006). Cooling of the West Spitsbergen current: Isopycnal diffusion by topographic vorticity waves. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 111(C8), C08012. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005jc002991>
- Nilsen, F., Skogseth, R., Vaardal-Lunde, J., & Inall, M. (2016). A simple shelf circulation model: Intrusion of Atlantic Water on the West Spitsbergen shelf. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 46(4), 1209–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1175/jpo-d-15-0058.1>
- Pavlov, A. K., Tverberg, V., Ivanov, B. V., Nilsen, F., Falk-Petersen, S., & Granskog, M. A. (2013). Warming of Atlantic Water in two west Spitsbergen fjords over the last century (1912–2009). *Polar Research*, 32(1), 11206. <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v32i0.11206>
- Polyakov, I. V., Pnyushkov, A. V., Alkire, M. B., Ashik, I. M., Baumann, T. M., Carmack, E. C., et al. (2017). Greater role for Atlantic inflows on sea-ice loss in the Eurasian basin of the Arctic Ocean. *Science*, 356(6335), 285–291. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aai8204>
- Saloranta, T. M., & Haugan, P. M. (2004). Northward cooling and freshening of the warm core of the West Spitsbergen Current. *Polar Research*, 23(1), 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v23i1.6268>
- Scholzen, C., Schuler, T. V., & Gilbert, A. (2021). Sensitivity of subglacial drainage to water supply distribution at the Kongsfjord basin, Svalbard. *The Cryosphere*, 15(6), 2719–2738. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-15-2719-2021>
- Serreze, M. C., & Barry, R. G. (2011). Processes and impacts of arctic amplification: A research synthesis. *Global and Planetary Change*, 77(1–2), 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2011.03.004>
- Shchepetkin, A. F., & McWilliams, J. C. (2005). The regional oceanic modeling system (ROMS): A split-explicit, free-surface, topography-following-coordinate oceanic model. *Ocean Modelling*, 9(4), 347–404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2004.08.002>
- Skamarock, W., Klemp, J., Dudhia, J., Gill, D., Barker, D., Duda, M., et al. (2008). A description of the advanced research WRF version 3. *NCAR Technical Note NCAR/TN-475+STR* (p. 113).
- Skogseth, R., Olivier, L. L. A., Nilsen, F., Falck, E., Fraser, N., Tverberg, V., et al. (2020). Variability and decadal trends in the Isfjorden (Svalbard) ocean climate and circulation – An indicator for climate change in the European Arctic. *Progress in Oceanography*, 187, 102394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2020.102394>
- Skogseth, R., Tverberg, V., Walczowski, W., & Sundfjord, A. (2019). Kongsfjorden transect CTD data 1906–2016 [Dataset]. *Norwegian Polar Institute*. <https://doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2019.074a215c>
- Stigebrandt, A. (1981). A mechanism governing the estuarine circulation in deep, strongly stratified fjords. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 13(2), 197–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0302-3524\(81\)80076-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0302-3524(81)80076-x)
- Stigebrandt, A. (2012). Hydrodynamics and circulation of fjords. *Encyclopedia of lakes and reservoirs*, 327, 344.
- Straneo, F., & Cenedese, C. (2015). The dynamics of Greenland's glacial fjords and their role in climate. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 7(1), 89–112. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010213-135133>
- Straneo, F., Hamilton, G. S., Sutherland, D. A., Stearns, L. A., Davidson, F., Hammill, M. O., et al. (2010). Rapid circulation of warm subtropical waters in a major glacial fjord in East Greenland. *Nature Geoscience*, 3(3), 182–186. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo764>
- Strzelewicz, A., Przyborska, A., & Walczowski, W. (2022). Increased presence of Atlantic Water on the shelf south-west of Spitsbergen with implications for the Arctic fjord Hornsund. *Progress in Oceanography*, 200, 102714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2021.102714>
- Sundfjord, A., Albreetsen, J., Kasajima, Y., Skogseth, R., Kohler, J., Nuth, C., et al. (2017). Effects of glacier runoff and wind on surface layer dynamics and Atlantic Water exchange in Kongsfjorden, Svalbard; a model study. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 187, 260–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2017.01.015>
- Svendsen, H. (1980). Exchange processes above sill level between fjords and coastal water. In *Fjord Oceanography* (pp. 355–361). Springer US.
- Svendsen, H., Beszczynska-Møller, A., Hagen, J. O., Lefauconnier, B., Tverberg, V., Gerland, S., et al. (2002). The physical environment of Kongsfjorden–Krossfjorden, an Arctic fjord system in Svalbard. *Polar Research*, 21(1), 133–166. <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v21i1.6479>
- Taylor, K. E. (2001). Summarizing multiple aspects of model performance in a single diagram. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 106(D7), 7183–7192. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000jd900719>
- Teigen, S. H., Nilsen, F., & Gjevik, B. (2010). Barotropic instability in the West Spitsbergen current. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 115(C7), C07016. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009jc005996>
- Teigen, S. H., Nilsen, F., Skogseth, R., Gjevik, B., & Beszczynska-Møller, A. (2011). Baroclinic instability in the West Spitsbergen current. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 116(C7), C07012. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011jc006974>
- Tesi, T., Muschitiello, F., Mollenhauer, G., Miserocchi, S., Langone, L., Ceccarelli, C., et al. (2021). Rapid Atlantification along the Fram Strait at the beginning of the 20th century. *Science Advances*, 7(48), eabj2946. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abj2946>
- Torsvik, T., Albreetsen, J., Sundfjord, A., Kohler, J., Sandvik, A. D., Skarðhamar, J., et al. (2019). Impact of tidewater glacier retreat on the fjord system: Modeling present and future circulation in Kongsfjorden, Svalbard. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 220, 152–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2019.02.005>
- Tverberg, V., Skogseth, R., Cottier, F., Sundfjord, A., Walczowski, W., Inall, M. E., et al. (2019). The Kongsfjorden transect: Seasonal and inter-annual variability in hydrography. In *Advances in polar ecology* (pp. 49–104). Springer International Publishing.

- Van Pelt, W., & Kohler, J. (2015). Modelling the long-term mass balance and firm evolution of glaciers around Kongsfjorden, Svalbard. *Journal of Glaciology*, *61*(228), 731–744. <https://doi.org/10.3189/2015jog14j223>
- van Pelt, W., Pohjola, V., Pettersson, R., Marchenko, S., Kohler, J., Luks, B., et al. (2019). A long-term dataset of climatic mass balance, snow conditions, and runoff in Svalbard (1957–2018). *The Cryosphere*, *13*(9), 2259–2280. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-13-2259-2019>
- Vihlakari, M. (2020). PlotSvalbard: PlotSvalbard - plot research data from Svalbard on maps. *R package version 0.9.2*. Retrieved from <https://github.com/MikkoVihlakari/PlotSvalbard>
- Walczowski, W., & Piechura, J. (2007). Pathways of the Greenland Sea warming. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *34*(10), L10608. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007gl029974>
- Wang, C. (2019). Rutgers ROMS coupled with buoyant plume theory (BPT). Retrieved from <https://github.com/ChuningWang/roms-iceplume>